

The Management of the Social and the Outdoor Advertising Media in Political Campaign Activities

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ABSTRACT

The social and the outdoor advertising media are medium that is often used in political campaign activity in Indonesia. Both media are packaged and managed attractively in hopes of persuading the public to choose certain parties or politicians. Based on this condition, the writer was interested to understand how to manage campaign media in political parties, especially the social and the outdoor advertising media. Then, to examine this problem, the writer used the qualitative method to design a single case study as a method to analyze the problem. This research is generally in the form of descriptions, narratives, data, images or statements obtained from research subjects, both directly and indirectly related to the management of social and outdoor advertising media in political campaign activities carried out by the DPC of PDI-P Tangerang Indonesia. The results of the study show that the use of social and outdoor advertising media must be well planned, communicated and evaluated in order to increase the credibility of political parties. So that it can be concluded that DPC of PDI-P integrates the functions of digital social and outdoor advertising media simultaneously, considering that the two media can target different audiences. The social media used in political campaigns, i.e., online media consists of websites and social media such as Instagram, Twitter, Facebook, WA Group. Then outdoor media includes banners that can be reached by the public in their neighborhood. To optimize the function of social and outdoor advertising media, the DPC PDI-P Tangerang also conducts media management processes including segmenting constituent stages, selecting campaign media, arranging political messages, controlling and monitoring media campaigns, conducting media campaign effectiveness surveys, carrying out the process assessment, and finally processing an improvement.

Keywords: Social media, outdoor advertising media, political campaigns.

INTRODUCTION

The mature democracy system can be realized if the high public participation can be realized. All citizens who have fulfilled the constitutional requirements as voters must also cast their votes on the general election. In this condition, each individual citizen has the same right to elect and to be elected. Through this democratic system, all citizens without recognizing social strata have the same opportunity and rights in determining the fate of the nation every five years. But in fact, the current level of participation of the younger generation in politics is often the subject of debate. This is because the younger generation is seen as skeptical of politics.

The young generation is often seen as a group of people who are least concerned with political issues, which often experience a breakup with their communities, who are not interested in political processes and political issues, which have a low level of trust in politicians and are cynical about various political and government institutions (Haste & Hogan, 2006). Data show that young people who join a political party is relatively small, and they tend to be abstentions on Elections (EACEA, 2012). In the other hand, the role of the younger generation in political events is very important to the development of a good democratic system.

In Indonesia, the numbers that do not vote at Election (abstentions) are increasingly high. It is as the data were no legislative elections in 2004; the number of abstentions reached 15.9 percent. That number increased in the first and second round of presidential elections. The number of abstentions during the 2004 presidential election reached 21.8 percent and 23.4 percent. Furthermore, in the 2009 election, the number increased to 29.1 percent abstention. In the same year's presidential election, the number of voters who did not use their votes amounted to 28.3 percent. Then the existence of abstentions continues in the 2014 legislative elections, with 24.89 percent of voters entering this category. At the time of the 2014 presidential election, the abstention rate reached its highest level of about 30 percent of the number of voters (<https://tirto.id>).

Elections are important in determining the future of the country, where voting in elections is one form of political participation. But political participation is not solely measured by voting during elections. Basically there are many forms of political participation such as: sending letters (messages) to government officials, participating in protests or demonstrations, becoming members of political parties,

becoming members of community organizations, running for public office, giving contributions to parties or politicians, to participate in fundraising events (Morissan, 2016: 98).

It cannot be denied that political parties are political institutions that are oriented to seize power, and then manage those powers according to party ideology. Therefore, various political parties are competitive in preparing various political communication strategies, including preparing the right media for means of political communication. The strength of selected media is taken into account, given the very diverse types of media ranging from electronic mass media, printed media, digital media, to social media that is currently in demand by the people. The political message that is incorporated in these media has an important role in public opinion. Media as a source of opinion, not all media content can be controlled by political parties. Media coverage, political news, political dialogue and various media publicity can be controlled by political parties. One of the efforts of political parties in controlling the contents of the media is by renting mass media space. One way to rent media space is by political advertising.

The Indonesian Democratic Party of Struggle (*PDIP*) as the winning party of the 2014 election is certainly faced with an uneasy challenge, in which the *PDIP* must defend the victory. As the saying goes, maintaining is even more difficult than winning. *PDIP* certainly does not expect to repeat the failure of several previous party winners. Therefore various political communication strategies were intensely launched. Then in the upcoming 2019 Legislative Election, the *PDI-P DPC* Tangerang targets 15 seats in the Tangerang Regional Representative Council (*DPRD*). This was conveyed by the Chairperson of the *PDI-P DPC* in Tangerang, Irvansyah when registering prospective legislators to the Tangerang Election Committee Office. Currently, there are 7 seats in the *DPRD*. In meeting the target of 15 seats, each electoral district is certain to add at least one seat. For that, said Irvan, in filling out 15 seats in the upcoming 2019 Election, his party maximized them by fulfilling all quota determined by the Election Committee. All of the candidates have been well selected and has quality in accordance with what the community needs (<https://lensapena.id>).

In addition, the *PDI-P* Tangerang was optimistic that it could win 15 seats in the *DPRD* in the upcoming legislative elections. This was conveyed by Chairperson of the *PDI-P* Tangerang Irvansyah. As many as 70 forms were taken by candidates, as many as 65 forms had been returned to the local *PDIP* Office in Tigaraksa. He said that he planned to submit the form to the *PDI-P* in Jakarta on May 30, 2018. In the selection of candidates, it was conducted strictly. He also hopes that a cadre will be born who understands people's problems, not just for their own interests and groups. "Women's representation reaches 30 percent. That is, there are five cadres who become legislators in the region," he said (<http://liputanbanten.co.id>).

These targets are certainly not easy to achieve, where party machinery must be able to work hard and formulate various mature and comprehensive strategies. Referring to these conditions, the *PDI-P* Tangerang has prepared various strategies for political communication in a mature manner, including optimizing social and outdoor advertising media as a means to convey party political messages. Referring to these targets, it is certainly interesting to manage social and outdoor advertising media in political campaign activities carried out by the *PDI-P* Tangerang. The purpose of this study is to understand how to manage campaign media in political parties, by analyzing what media are used in political campaign activities, and how to manage them.

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.2.1 Political Communication

Political communication is a conversation to influence in the life of the state. Political communication can also be an art of designing what is possible (the art of possible) and can even be an art of designing that is not possible (the art of impossible) (Arifin, 2011: 1). Littlejohn further in Political communication theory explains the purpose process in which elected leaders, media, and citizens use messages to build meaning about political practice. When people use power to support public interests, their messages and interactions are a strategic means to influence public policy (Rahman, 2018: 1168).

The purpose of political communication according to Arifin (2012) is that among others: 1) forming a good political image in the audience. The political image is formed based on information received, both directly and through political media, including social and mass media that work to convey general and actual political messages, 2) build public opinion, where public opinion is feedback from the public to politicians or political parties. Public opinion can be interpreted as opinions, attitudes, feelings, predictions,

establishment, and expectations of average group individuals in society, 3) building political participation and political policies. Political participant is “audience members” who are not indifferent, but active, both in watching the political message of the political communicator, but co-responding and performing in line with the politicians, and 4) election, where the success of political communication is measured by the number of votes obtained through elections that are clean, free, direct and confidential (Rahman, 2018: 851) .

Then the elements of political communication according to Nimmo in Cangara (2009), which consists of sources from 1) Political communicators. All the party gets involved in process message delivery. These parties can be shaped individual, groups, organizations, institution, or government, 2) Political Message. Political Message is a statement that delivered well written or not, inform symbol or verbal containing element political for example political speeches, laws, etc., 3) channel or political media. In this developing era, media mass considered as channels that best to do political communication process, 4) Political Message Recipients. All society expected give a response to message political communication, and 5) Influence. The effect is how much measure far message politics is acceptable and understood (La Nora, 2014: 50-51).

2.2.2 Political Campaign Media

The use of the internet as a political campaign media is one of the political communication strategies that are currently in demand at this time. This is because people use various social media platform opportunities to express, promote themselves, and publish them (Elmer. 2015: 1). Then social media also provides a form of data that users make multi-modular (through a combination of text, hyperlinks, images, videos, music, etc.) (Brooker et al. 2016: 1).

For example, in the presidential political campaign, is now routinely and actively using digital media to reach, involve and mobilize voters (Bimber & Davis, 2003; Foot & Schneider, 2006; Kreiss, 2012; Stromer-Galley, 2014). The limitations of social media allow a rapid response, foster a supportive community and push their agenda onto the national stage (Kreiss, 2012; Stromer-Galley, 2014). This is as in the process of his political campaign Barack Obama employed more than 100 staff and invested \$ 47 million in social media outreach, which included regularly posting political updates, monitoring these messages and communicating with supporters. As can be seen from this example and more recent developments, social media has become a critical domain of communication and political competition (Hsin. 2017: 77)

In democratic activities, it cannot be denied that the campaign is an important thing to do, in order to gain public trust. This is as stated by Gronbeck (1978) and Norris (1999) who explained that the campaign has various functions, including winning the battle of ideas, changing and mobilizing supporters, giving supporters of claims and topics of information, and so on. This campaign is usually carried out through channels of technology-mediated communication (Jensen. 2017: 22).

Apart from using social media, political communication media that are often used by political parties and politicians is outdoor media. The categories of outdoor advertising are also diverse including posters, in-vehicle advertisements, banners, billboards (headbands, neon signs, lightless billboards), hot air balloons, banners, and etc.

Advertising is part of the marketing tool for all businesses that are currently or will be undertaken by the community. The existence of advertisements makes the message or information of a product, service or organization of events can be seen by the wider community, especially the community that has been determined by advertisers or companies as the target. Ads that are made have the effect of informing various kinds of things, especially with the help of existing advertising media. Moreover, with outdoor advertising media that we can easily see and meet on the streets because they are large, they can be seen from a distance and can be seen at night because they have lights that can light up advertising information (Saputra & Herawati, 2014: 2).

2.2.3 Political Participation and Beginner Voters

According to Christian Wulff, Indonesia is the largest country that has successfully implemented democracy, as the most Muslim country in the world. This was stated by the German Federal President, Christian Wulff when delivering a public lecture at the Floating Auditorium of the UI Depok Library. Christian places Indonesia as a successful democracy after India and America. He hopes that German and Indonesian relations can become a more intense relationship in the fields of economy and world peace (cited in Tempo, December 1, 2011).

Christian Wulff's opinion is relevant to the increasing number of community participation in democratic activities. Then according to Dewey (1927) and Näsström (2003) states that democracy is based on the community and for the community. For a number of ethical and practical reasons, democracy is considered appropriate to involve the public in jointly determining to determine and change its situation. Then all people have voting rights in governance and development processes (Scholte, 2014: 3). Then Mazzuca and Munck (2014) state that democracy offers solutions to problems related to the state (Wang and Yiqing, 2018: 1).

To create democratic stability, public participation in democratic activities must continue to increase. Therefore understanding democracy and politics must continue to be extended to the community. Political communication, political socialization, political image, ultimately lead to goals and objectives, namely the achievement of political participation and participation in the process of determining political policy. Political participation or people's participation in political agendas, very important democracy (the cornerstone of democracy), especially in a representative democracy (Arifin, 2012: 235-266). To realize a mature democratic system, high public participation is needed. But the level of participation of the younger generation in politics is often a matter of debate. The young generation is often seen as a group of people who are least concerned with political issues, which often experience a breakup with their communities, who are not interested in political processes and political issues, which have a low level of trust in politicians and are cynical about various political and government institutions (Pirie & Worcester, 1998; Haste & Hogan, 2006).

The participation of audiences or people in political activities, especially in voting in general elections and influencing public policy, is the consequence or effect of very important political communication. Then people in democratic countries can participate in political life in at least three different ways: 1) People can be involved in the public arena to promote and convey their demands to those who want to hear. Example: join the demonstration, 2) the community can make the legislative body or the executive institution as the target of the political message to be conveyed. For example: sign a petition, and 3) the community can be involved in the selection process of people who want to occupy public positions. Example: voting in elections or running for public office (Morissan, 2016).

RESEARCH METHOD

This study uses qualitative methods with a single case study design. This research is generally in the form of descriptions, narratives, data, images or statements obtained from research subjects, both directly and indirectly related to the management of social and outdoor advertising media in political campaign activities carried out by the *DPC* of *PDI-P* Tangerang Indonesia. The main data sources in qualitative research are words, actions, and the rest are additional data such as documents and others. In this section the data types are divided into words and actions, written data sources, photographs, and statistics.

The object of the research was the *DPC* of *PDI-P* Tangerang; then the speakers were selected speakers from the *DPC* of *PDI-P* Tangerang and Beginner Voters. The speakers were detailed as follows: Chairperson of *DPC* Irvansyah Asmat, Secretary of *DPC* Akmaludin Nugraha, Winning Division Didin Muhidin, *OKK* division Surdin, then Beginner Voter Arif Rohman and Siti Aam Fatriah. The location of this research is in the office of the *DPC* of *PDI-P* Tangerang. Located in the town square of the city block GM 6 No. 3 Klp. Indah, Tangerang, Banten 15117.

The process of collecting data refers to several stages. They are the process of interviews, observation and documentation study. Then the data analysis technique used refers to the opinion of Miles and Huberman which includes three activities together: data reduction, Data that has been classified based on this category is then sorted again, and if there are those that are not in accordance with the aspects studied, the data is discarded, data presentation. In this process, researchers group similar things into categories or groups of one, groups of two, groups of three, and so on, and conclusions (verification) are compiled into a conclusion, where this conclusion is the result of research that can answer research questions previously formulated (Haryati, 2018: 176) .

After the data is collected, the next step is to do the data validation process using the source triangulation technique. Through this technique, researchers compare and check back on the degree of trust in information obtained by: (1) comparing observational data with interview data (2) comparing the consistency of the answers of the sources by comparing what the public speakers say for example, with what is said privately (3) comparing one's perspective, for example in this case that is comparing the opinions

of various predetermined sources (4) comparing the results of interviews with the contents of a document (literature) relating to discussion (Irawan, 2018: 75836).

DISCUSSION

Recently the numbers of non-voters (abstentions) in Election in Indonesia are increasingly high. In the 2004 legislative elections, the number of abstentions reached 15.9 percent. That number increased in the first and second round of presidential elections. The number of abstentions during the 2004 presidential election reached 21.8 percent and 23.4 percent. Furthermore, in the 2009 legislative election, the number of abstentions increased to 29.1 percent. In the same year’s presidential election, the number of voters who did not use their votes amounted to 28.3 percent. Then the existence of abstentions continues in the 2014 legislative elections, with 24.89 percent of voters entering this category. At the time of the 2014 presidential election, the abstention rate reached its highest level of 30 percent more than the number of voters (<https://tirto.id>).

Looking at the conditions and data, it is certainly a slap for political parties who will contest politics in the 2019 general election. Now political parties are also increasingly competing to get the hearts and voices of voters, especially for beginner voters. Beginner voters are considered as voters who still have not made a choice, unlike the old voters where they tend to have choices. Various strategies for political communication were carried out, including by choosing media that are often used and accessible to voters.

The choice of media is certainly very important, considering that the media is a bridge that connects information between political parties and politicians and the people. In addition, the media of political communication can also be understood as a means of delivering information to the electorate. Although the effectiveness of this campaign media does not guarantee the electability of parties or politicians, at least that information has reached the target.

If it is classified, the political communication media used by the *DPC* of *PDI-P* Tangerang is divided into two, social and outdoor advertising media. The explanation regarding the flow of the use of campaign media can be seen in the picture of the framework below:

Figure 1. Thinking Framework

From the frame of mind, it can be seen that the basis of the use of political communication media is the target of political parties, the acquisition of vote, which is then communicated through the media campaign consisting of social and outdoor advertising media. After the message is conveyed through the campaign media, then the message will arrive at the voters, thus the hope that is the interest of voters to choose the *PDI-P* party in Tangerang.

To be elected, political parties should have developed and consistently strengthened brand awareness. According to Durianto et al. (2001: 54), brand awareness alone can be concluded as a potential buyer, in this case, the constituents to recognize, recall a brand as part of a product category, in this case, a particular political party. Referring to this opinion, political parties need to enhance strong relations between political parties with a strong vision. One of the ways is to convey various political messages of the party through interesting and accessible media for voters.

This is inseparable from the position (status) and the role of political parties that are very important in every democratic system. The party plays a very strategic liaison role between government processes and citizens. Political parties open the widest opportunity for people to participate in political and governmental activities. Because through political parties a responsible government can be realized and fight for public interests and prevent arbitrary government actions. As an organization, political parties are ideally intended to activate and mobilize the people, represent certain interests, and provide a way of compromising competing opinions and providing a means of peaceful political leadership succession (Natalia, 2015: 53).

However, the fact shows that public participation in choosing has fluctuated, for example, the number of beginner voters in the implementation of the election of Tangerang Regent and Deputy Regent in 2018 is around 3% of the total number of permanent voters in Tangerang, with the total permanent voters of 1.843.188. At least there is around 11 percent of the beginner voters from the total permanent voter's list in Tangerang. That is, in the range of 206.262 people from a total of 1.875.124. Beginner voters are identical to the millennial generation. The generation tends to be more about information technology. Almost all of the beginner voters in Tangerang have used the internet as a necessity for everything. Gadgets, in this case, are no longer new, even applications such as Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and other social media are identified by the Party as a medium of political communication.

Practically, the *DPC* of *PDI-P* Tangerang uses social and outdoor advertising media. This is because the party realizes that even though digital technology has advanced, outdoor media is still needed to target the community at large. But the dominant political communication media that is used is social media. Social media is used as a medium of political communication because the political message is prioritized for young voters because the *DPC* of *PDI-P* Tangerang considers that 100% of the voters begin using gadgets. The social media used are Instagram, Facebook, and Whatsapp Group. Then the outdoor media used are banners and baligho.

The stages of management of political communication media run continuously, where this stage can be simulated in the following figure:

Figure 2: The process of managing campaign media

The process of managing political communication media carried out by the *DPC* of *PDI-P* Tangerang is certainly not instant, but through several stages, Firstly, segmenting constituents. In this activity, the *DPC* of *PDI-P* Tangerang was able to map constituent targets by identifying the types of sex, age, occupation, and status. Based on this identification, the average beginner voters are among students and young workers targeted through social media. This is because young people prefer social media in finding various information, including political information. But outdoor media is also used to reinforce messages communicated through social media. But outdoor media is intended to strengthen the effectiveness of social media. In this 2019 election, the *DPC* of *PDI-P* Tangerang tried to prioritize beginner voters. Party resources that carry out mapping is *Balitbang*. *Balitbang* conducted a mapping process on the situation and conditions as well as the trend of beginner voters, especially voters in Tangerang.

Secondly, selecting the media of political communication. The media used in targeting new voters are more dominant in the use of online media, one of which is the website and social media such as Instagram, Twitter, Facebook, Whatsapp Group. Besides, the *DPC* of *PDI-P* Tangerang also uses outdoor media such as banners that can be reached by the public in their neighborhood. Campaign media is not only a medium for delivering political messages, but can be used as a medium of political education and a means of accommodating public aspirations. Media as a means of political education means the media is used by political parties and legislative candidates and regional heads to be able to provide information and provide explanations regarding programs that will be implemented if elected, but all that is delivered must be in accordance with the facts that exist and can provide knowledge to the community about the meaning of the program promised. Then the media as a means of accommodating people's aspirations means that the media are expected to be used as a means of communication with their constituents.

Thirdly, compiling messages of political communication that are in accordance with the characteristics of the constituents, especially beginner voters. Therefore, the *DPC* of *PDI-P* Tangerang composes a message of political communication in a present and light manner so that it is easily understood by the beginner voters. For examples, political messages conveyed such as political education, social messages such as encouragement to stay away from drugs, come to polling stations, and some social activities. Various political messages on social media are generally lightly packaged and easily understood by beginner voters. The same thing is packaged in outdoor media such as banners.

Fourthly, controlling activities carried out by the *DPC* of *PDI-P* Tangerang in the process of building and strengthening brand awareness among voters conducted through various methods. The activities and steps in carrying out control are (1) controlling the message delivered to outdoor media. At this stage, cadres routinely control the banners and billboards not to be sabotaged by irresponsible parties. In this context, the *DPC* of *PDI-P* Tangerang carried out logistical monitoring and campaign demonstration with the voluntary support of party cadres and sympathizers. (2) Controlling of public opinion that develops on social media related to issues or negative hoaxes that afflict the party. This was done by looking at responses or comments that were scattered on social media published by the *DPC* of *PDI-P* Tangerang. If this happens, the party provides an explanation or clarification. If this is indicated to be detrimental to the party and has a criminal element, then it is possible to continue in the legal sphere.

Fifthly, conducting a public perception survey. This survey was intended so that the *DPC* of *PDI-P* Tangerang would know the effectiveness of campaign media. This survey was conducted by the Internal Survey institution called REKODE. Besides, the party was also assisted by independent surveyor Polcomm Institute. Based on the survey results, it was shown that the Party which received the highest support was 22.92%, one of them was the result of a survey conducted by an independent surveyor Polcomm Institute. In addition, political parties are considered necessary to consider input both from surveys formed by internal parties and credible independent survey institutions. The survey is only one tool of many instruments in collecting data and political mapping. Then in a certain moment, *PDI-P* uses political consultants. At this stage, the survey is carried out directly to the audience or constituents without looking at the background of the organization or the community. In this context, the survey was conducted for all beginner voters in accordance with the criteria based on legislation.

Sixthly, do the assessment process. This assessment process is carried out after the Monitoring Team goes to the field and has made reports and records which are the material for assessment. Through the data obtained from the monitoring team, the *DPC* of *PDI-P* Tangerang assessed the realization of the program. In addition to the data from the field survey, this assessment process also examines data from the results of internal and external surveys. The results of this assessment are certainly recommended for various similar activities which will be carried out in the future time.

Finally, the remedial process. At this stage, the *DPC* of *PDI-P* Tangerang realized various recommendations from the evaluation stages. This stage of remedy is an absolute and must be done, considering that this refers to the recommendation of the *DPC* of the *PDI-P* Tangerang evaluation meeting. Every program implemented must refer to recommendations and improvements given to similar programs that have been implemented. These various stages and processes aim to increase the electability of the party, and finally, the party can get a high vote in the electoral process.

The most important thing in this democratic process is increasing public participation in the political process. Public participation in the political arena is an attempt by political parties to involve "members of

the public” not to be indifferent, to be active, not only to pay attention to the political messages of political communicators or politicians but also to respond and dialogue with the politicians. Even political participants collaborate and together with political communicators or politicians so that they play a role as political communicators (Arifin, 2012: 178-216). In this context, the involvement of beginner voters in the event certainly helps political parties to communicate and persuade young people to be actively involved in these activities.

CONCLUSION

The findings of the study show that the use of social and outdoor advertising media must be well planned, communicated and evaluated in order to increase the credibility of political parties. It can be concluded that the *DPC* of *PDI-P* Tangerang integrates the functions of digital social and outdoor advertising media simultaneously, remembering the two media can target different audiences. The social media used in political campaigns are online media, consists of websites and social media such as Instagram, Twitter, Facebook, Whatsapp Group. Then outdoor media includes banners that can be reached by the public in their neighborhood. To optimize the function of social and outdoor advertising media, the *DPC* of *PDI-P* Tangerang also conducts media management processes including segmenting constituent stages, selecting campaign media, arranging political messages, controlling and monitoring media campaigns, conducting media campaign effectiveness surveys, carrying out the process assessment, and finally processing an improvement.

Referring to the study, it is advisable to do the following activities: (1) optimize the social media in a way put through a social media management of official political parties more interactive with a variety of customized content styles of millennial voters , (2) control public opinion in social media, the party should be equipped with a media monitoring application, so that the party can early know the positioning of the party and the party can easily detect various attacks in the virtual world in an easy and practical way, (3) making outdoor media such as banners should involve the participation of the young generation and sympathizers of the party, so that the messages conveyed are more appropriate to their needs and (4) are advised to carry out surveys conducted by independent survey institutions regarding which media are the most used, so that these findings can be used as a considered evaluation.

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